

LINGUISTIC STYLISTICS IN CROSS-CULTURAL LITERARY TRANSLATION

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This article studies how stylistic features in literature, particularly metaphors, repetition, rhythm, irony, sentence structure and tone can be translated from one language to another, more importantly, to other cultures. Literary style plays an important role in creating emotions, helps express author's true intentions, his voice, shaping atmosphere of a work, as well as conveying culturally embedded meanings. Understanding how these elements function is essential to preserve the artistic and cultural value of literary text in translation.

In today's world, where cultures are becoming closer every day, literature remains one of the most powerful ways for people to truly understand each other. Through translation, it is easier for readers to step into another culture's way of thinking and feeling. They discover its history, values and unique beauty of the language. However, the very elements that make a text true literature is its style, the texture of its language and the emotions it evokes are the hardest to preserve when a work is translated into another language.¹

Linguistic stylistics explores how language in a literary text becomes more than just a tool for conveying meaning: it turns into something expressive, vivid, and emotionally powerful. One of the key concepts is foregrounding. This occurs when the author purposely makes certain words, sounds, or sentence structures stand out so that readers cannot ignore them. Foregrounding in two main forms: *deviation*, when the writer breaks the rules of language (for example through unusual vocabulary or word order), and *parallelism*, which involves repetitions, rhythm, balanced structures that build a harmony and power.²

Translating literature between very different languages and cultures significantly challenging. Because of cultural and linguistic differences, many stylistic devices have no direct equivalents. One of the most important mechanisms is *foregrounding*, which in Russian it's often called *выдвижение* or *актуализация*. In everyday speech, language follows predictable patterns. But in literature, an author may suddenly break the pattern, forcing the reader pause and pay attention. It's like a bright light flashing in a dark room, where our eyes drawn to it.³

Foregrounding works in two main ways:

- Deviation (*отклонение*). The author may break the rules of language, involves creating a new word, using unusual word order, creating a metaphor, or using an unexpected sound.

- Parallelism (*параллелизм*). In this case, the effect is created through repetition, repeating the same sounds (alliteration), similar sentence structures, a rhythmic pattern that gives a sense of balance and emphasis.

¹ Baker, M. Towards a methodology for investigating the style of a literary translator. 2000.pp. 241–266.

² Boase-Beier, J. Stylistic approaches to translation. St. Jerome Publishing, 2006. pp. 78–92.

³ Leech G. N. A linguistic guide to English poetry. Longman. 1969.pp. 74–89.

These stylistic effects often create difficulties in translation. What sounds natural and powerful in one language may lose its impact in another.⁴

For example, a Russian literature text may combine satire, fantasy, and philosophical reflection, drawing on Soviet-era irony and biblical references. Translating such a text into English requires dealing with significant differences between the two languages. Russian allows more flexible syntax and often relies on rich idiomatic expressions and cultural-specific references, whereas English tends to follow a more fixed sentence and prefers greater conciseness.

«Однажды весной, в час небывало жаркого заката, в Москве, на Патриарших прудах, появились два гражданина. Первый из них, одетый в летнюю серенькую пару, был маленького роста, упитан, лыс, свою приличную шляпу пирожком нес в руке, а на хорошо выбритом лице его помещались сверхъестественных размеров очки в черной роговой оправе...»⁵

The passage begins with "Once upon a springtime..." which gives it a fairy-tale-like opening, only to drop into the mundane reality of everyday Soviet Moscow. The humor emerges from small exaggerations: the hat describes as being "like a little pie", and the bald head, though "perfectly shaved"

English:

"At the sunset hour of one warm spring day two men were to be seen at Patriarch's Ponds. The first of them—aged about forty, dressed in a greyish summer suit—was short, dark-haired, plump and bald; he carried a respectable cloth cap in his hand, and his neatly shaven face was adorned with black horn-rimmed spectacles of preternatural size..."⁶

English version 2:

"At the hour of the hot spring sunset two citizens appeared at the Patriarch's Ponds. The first of them, dressed in a grey summer suit, was short, well-fed, bald, carried his respectable pie-shaped hat in his hand, and on his well-shaven face were perched spectacles of supernatural dimensions in a black horn frame..."

There are notable differences in both translations. The first translator breaks the sentence with a dash and shortens the description, creating light, gentle humor. The second keeps the long, detailed chain of descriptors, producing a humor that is sharper, slightly dark, and closer to the tone of the original text. Both translations convey the two well-dressed men calmly sitting in a park, but the nuance of humor and strangeness shifts.

Uzbek:

"Bir kuni bahorda, g'ayrioddiy issiq quyosh botishi vaqtida, Moskvada, Patriarx hovuzlari yonida ikki fuqaro paydo bo'ldi. Ulardan birinchisi, yozgi kulrang kostyum kiygan, past bo'yli, semiz, kal, o'zining munosib shlyapasini pirojok shaklida qo'lida ko'tarib yurgan, yaxshi qir qilgan yuzida qora rog' ramkali g'ayritabiiy katta ko'zoynaklar joylashgan edi"⁷

⁴ Creswell, J. W., Poth, C. N. Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches 4th ed. SAGE Publications, 2018. Pp.12-15.

⁵ Bulgakov, Mikhail. The Master and Margarita., 1984. p3.

⁶ Michael Glenny, The Master and Margarita by Mikhail Bulgakov London: Collins and Harvill Press, 1967. p4.

⁷ Qodir Mirmuhamedov (tarjimon), Usta va Margarita by Mixail Bulgakov Sharq nashriyoti, 1990s–2010. p5.

This version has a lively, folk-like flow that fits the Uzbek reading style. It is a strong faithful adaptation that conveys the humor, strangeness and tension of the original. Uzbek literature often favors long, piled-up descriptions with too many details. Everyday words like “*semiz*” (plump/chubby) and “*kal*” (bald) give the text a colloquial, playful tone of people joke in spoken Uzbek.

The analysis demonstrated that translating literary texts required a careful balance between accuracy and the preserving the stylistic and artistic features of the original work. Comparing the two English translations revealed how different translation strategies can produce different effects. The first translation focused on clarity and readability, breaking the long Russian sentence into shorter parts. This made the text more accessible for English readers, but it slightly reduced the slow narrative rhythm and the subtle ironic tone of the original passage. The second translation, by keeping the long chain of descriptions and unusual details, captured the strange, satirical, and slightly absurd atmosphere that characterizes the original narrative. It preserved the stylistic flow of the source text more faithfully and maintained the gradual storytelling typical of the original. The study confirmed that translators often face a choice between structural accuracy and stylistic effect, and successful translation depends on the ability to recreate the artistic impact of the original text for readers in another language.

References:

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